
NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION USING AUTOENCODE NEURAL NETWORK**Zakiya Manzoor Khan**

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ABSTRACT

There is a wide range of applications for photodetectors in wireless sensing networks as well as environmental monitoring systems, while 3D materials contain gaps of different bands that can be used in different application fields. Graphene was used in this research as a semiconductor material to produce a photodetector operating with a wide range of wavelengths that useful in detecting waves of applied interest in the industrial field. The very small energy gap of a single Graphene layer under the grating in Gold based MSM nanostructure showed encourage behavior of electric field distribution upon the plasmonic surface. Also, the measured optical properties and detector parameters gave acceptable results. The achieved results show that the best plasmonic surface, responsivity about 94.48 A/W, and detectivity about 5.408×10^{13} with lowest NEP of about 1.849×10^{-14} when using 1550 nm wavelength.

KEYWORDS: *Graphene, MSM-Photodetectors, I-V Characteristics, Detector parameters.*

1. INTRODUCTION

There are two sorts of devices for producing an electric signal when lit by light, they are: quantum and thermal threshold photodetectors. The incoming radiation's photons are absorbed in thermal photodetectors and raising the temperature of the substance, such as a bolometer. The thermocouple phenomenon turns the increase in temperature into an electrical current. At infrared and sub-millimeter wavelengths, thermal detectors are crucial and can be utilized likened to X-ray detectors [1]. Whereas, the quantum photodetectors in , a quantum threshold photodetector (also known as a photodiode), the incoming photons are absorbed inside the semiconductor material by interacting with electrons. [2]. Intrinsic and extrinsic varieties of semiconductor PDs exist. If a photon's energy exceeds the semiconductor's bandgap energy, an intrinsic (pure) PD will absorb it. Photoexcitation, which results in the photocurrent following the application of an external voltage, forms electron-hole pairs of atoms. On the other hand, an extrinsic Photo detector absorbs photons without exceeding the bandgap energy. As a result of the absorption of photons, electrons are moved from the holes in the valence band are caused by deep impurity defect levels within the bandgap to the conduction band. The depleted semiconductor region in both intrinsic and extrinsic photodetectors contains an electric field that serves to differentiate photogenerated electron-hole pairs. For high-speed operation,

the transit time must be as short as feasible. The depletion layer must be thick enough to allow for the absorption of a substantial portion of the incoming light[3].

In comparison to other photodetectors like traditional p-i-n photodiodes, metal-semiconductor-metal (MSM) photodetectors (PDs) provide an alluring advantage. According to Figure(1), an MSM photodetector is made up of interdigitated Schottky metal contacts on top of an active (absorption) layer . Since MSM photodetectors are naturally planar, they may be produced using current field effect transistor (FET) technology with just one photolithography process. Due to its low capacitance and relatively low dark currents, MSM photodetectors are highly fast devices (current produced without incident light). In contrast to p-i-n photodiodes, the responsivity (total signal produced from a given optical input) is relatively low. The main reasons for the low responsiveness are reflection from the surface metals and semiconductor surface, finite carrier lifetime as the carriers travel through the electrode gap before being collected, absorption of incident light outside the region in which photogenerated carriers can be collected by the electrodes, surface recombination currents, and deep traps within the semiconductor material, which may reduce the detected optical signal. Different conceptual factors are affecting the quantum efficiency of photodetectors, they are: responsivity, photoelectric current, quantum efficiency, noise, noise equivalent power, detectivity, Gain, and quantum efficiency properties. More details about such effective factors are given in the following sections [4].

Figure (1) MSM-PD [4].

2. Related work and our contribution

There a wealth of literature was produced in MSM-PD designing, but it varies greatly in terms of things like assumptions, materials employed, and even application restrictions. The most interesting ones related to investigations are made towards the viability of employing graphene to create MSM-PD are given in the following:

2.1 Related Work

MSM Photodetectors-related research areas are quite popular right now. To acquire effective technologies that may be applied in the industrial sphere, several techniques have been created. The following section shows a detailed discussion of the key pieces of literature that offered novel approaches to the subject of interest:

A.Müller, and etal (2008) described the fabrication and analysis structures of GaN membrane-supported MSM photodetector made using nanolithographic methods. The performances of the two

separate runs of MSM photodetectors, which had various MSM structural dimensions and different GaN membrane thicknesses, were analyzed. Unexpectedly high values for the responsiveness of the UV detectors, in the region of "50-100A/W," have been attained. with very low dark currents [4]. **Burak Yahya Kadem (2009)** We employed an n-type semiconductor as the substrate, two distinct metal types (Ni and Au) were used as Schottky contacts, and we used a (Ge-Au) alloy utilizing a thermal vacuum evaporation technique as the Ohmic contact. The tungsten source with a power range of (8.5 - 17 W) and a wavelength range of (400-1000 nm) was used. The detectors' parameters was examined with including their noise equivalent power, directivity, quantum efficiency, and spectral response [5]. **Yanbin An, and etal (2013)** constructed and described Photodetectors for metal semiconductor metal based on graphene/p-type Si Schottky junctions. The junction transport above 260 K is dominated by thermionic emission, with a 0.48 eV zero-bias barrier height. It is discovered this Fermi level shift in (Gr) is mostly responsible for the reverse-bias dependency of the barrier height. Response of MSM photodetectors is "0.11 A/W", and their ratio of the averaged photocurrent to the dark current is "4.55*10⁴mW⁻¹" [6]. **Subhrajit Mukherjee and etal (2014)** created visible to near-IR single silicon nanowire based MSM photodetectors that demonstrate outstanding responsiveness ">104 A/W" even in the absence of external bias. It has been demonstrated using finite-element based optical modeling that the rise in electric field is what causes the responsivity to grow as a function of nanowire diameter [7]. **GHADA DUSHAQ and etal (2017)** fabricated low-temperature two-step RF-PECVD that deposited photodetectors (MSM PDs) on silicon with germanium metal-semiconductor-metal. The photodetectors are properly optimized. The results showed that SBH may be successfully increased For electrons and holes, respectively, "0.3 eV" and "0.54 eV", respectively. Additionally, the (I_D) is greatly decreased by a factor of four or more. For a 1.0 V reverse bias applied, the measured I_{Dark} is 76 nA. Additionally, at that bias, the Germanium metal semiconductor metal structure had a photo responsiveness of "0.8A/W" [8]. **Shaili Sett and etal (2018)** suggested self-powered photodetectors that created using A single Germanium nanowire is used in the design of MSM devices. The self-powered devices have a strong photoresponse "Responsivity 103-105A/W" in the "300–1100 nm" wavelength range.. Throughout modeling, an asymmetric SBH is established the metal contacts of an Metal Semiconductor Metal device [9]. **Chun-Ying Huang, and etal (2020)** proposed Optoelectronic Integrated Circuits (OEICs) employ MSM photodetectors (PDs) due to they enable to be integrated into a simple circuit. In an MSM PD using an interdigital electrode that is symmetrical, the suggested technique achieved an asymmetric Schottky barrier height. underlying the connections of the MSM PDs, a portion of the a-IGZO film is subjected to a targeted application of surface fluorin plasma, which results in a localized oxygen shortage. The symmetrical interdigitate electrode of the a-IGZO MSM PD runs at zero bias and has "5 mA/W"responsiveness. At" 365 nm" and" 2 mW/cm² "light, the open circuit voltage is" 0.20 V "[10].

2.2 Our Contribution

The contribution of the present work is related to the employment of a single layer of graphene semiconductors with extremely small energy gaps underneath the grating in the MSM nanostructure, which is useful to investigate the degree of its impact on the plasmonic surface. In turn, the IV-

Characteristic of the MSM nanostructure and their impact on photodetectors' responsiveness are being studied. This is helpful in the search for novel photodetector designs that might function throughout a large portion of the electromagnetic spectrum.

3. Photodetector Performance Measures

Responsiveness (R) is the most important factor affect the performance of the photodetectors, it is the proportion between the output electrical signals (voltage or current) and the radiation power that was incident. Simply put, the photocurrent is the value of R for monochromatic light. is simply the photocurrent (I_{ph}) divided by the result of multiplying the the signal voltage, P_{in}: the signal voltage (P_{in}) by incident power radiation (P_{in}) as follows [11]:

$$R = I_{ph} / P_{in} \quad (amp/watt) \quad \dots (1)$$

The noise (I_n) occurred in a detector when radiation is a small voltage referred to as Dark current (I_D) that computed by the electron charge (e=1.6*10⁻¹⁹ c) as follows [12]:

$$I_n = (2e I_D)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

Also, another type of noise shows a little effect is the “Noise Equivalent Power”, which refers to the amount of root-mean-square radiant energy that must strike the detector for the RMS signal voltage or current at the detector's output to match the RMS noise voltage or current of predefined resistivity (R) as follows [13]:

$$NEP = \frac{I_n}{R} \quad \dots (3)$$

The detectivity (D) of the photo detector is the reciprocal of NEP, According to its definition, it is the signal-to-noise ratio for each unit of incident radiation power. [13]:

$$D = \frac{1}{NEP} = \frac{R}{I_n} \quad \dots (4)$$

While The amount of charge carriers that move back and forth between a detector's two contact electrodes each second (τ) for each photon absorbed each second (Tr),is known as photocurrent gain (G) which can be given by the following Eq.s (5 and 6) [14]:

$$G = \tau / T_r \quad \dots (5)$$

$$G = I_{ph} / I_D \quad \dots (6)$$

In another terminology, “τ”,and” T_r” is the carrier lifetime and the transit time respectively, which is expressed by the following relation:

$$T_r = \ell^2 / \mu \cdot V_B \quad \dots (7)$$

Where " ℓ " denotes the separation between the electrodes, " μ " denotes the majority carrier mobility, and " V_B " is the bias voltage supplied to the sample.

The Quantum Efficiency (η) is a quality indicator associated with responsivity (R) to a beam of λ wavelength. It measures how many elementary events there were compared to the total amount of photons that were incident; the quantum efficiency for an ideal detector is unity. [15]:

$$\eta = R \left(\frac{1240}{\lambda} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

4. DESIGNED MSM-PHOTODETECTOR

The suggested nanograting is created using electromagnetic simulation models from the Multiphysics module of the COMSOL program. “AC/DC Electric Current” and “Electromagnetic Wave Frequency

Domain (EWFD) are the two modules that make up these models. Finding the appropriate material to employ that can result in the optimum operating conditions is necessary to develop a photodetector design that operates across a broad spectrum. In order to produce the optimal PPS distribution, the optical properties of the grating such as: height, breadth, and number of gratings are tuned. In order to create a three-dimensional metal-semiconductor-metal (MSM) plasmonic surface, gold metal was used together with graphene semiconductor material.

The suggested metal semiconductor metal (MSM) design for a nanograting structure device is shown in the cross-section in Figure (2). In which the suggested design's plasmon surface area is 50 nm in width and (20nm) in height. The suggested MSM design is made up of three layers. The first is the lower background layer, which is made of gold with a (10nm) thickness; the second is a thin semiconductor layer of graphene with a (5nm) thickness; and the third is a gold grating with a (3nm) in width and (4nm) in height to achieve the best plasmonic surface during interaction. This gold grating is created using an aperture of a sub-wavelength (d) set in the space between two linear metal gratings of (H_g) height and (Λ) period and a thin, height-added dielectric layer covers the metal film (HWG). As the operation progresses, the incident electromagnetic wave ($h\nu$) excites the plasmon surface at the metal/air interface, creating an electric field (E) above and below the plasmon surface, which is denoted in the image by bold blue curving arrows (1). The device's optical improvements, such as transmission, absorption, reflection, and near-enhanced electric field, are then calculated using the EWFD module. While the ADEC module determines the device's current density increase by connecting the circuit to our design as shown in Figure (3). The improvements were identified utilizing a detection approach that operated in the visible to infrared spectrum.

Figure (2): Schematic graph of designed MSM-photodetector nanograting structure device.

Figure (3): Electric circuit of MSM-Photodetector.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The optical characteristics of the grating will be affected by the distribution of the electric field created when the used light falls on the designed plasmonic device, and this effect is closely related to the design employed to generate the plasmonic state. Figure (4) depicts the distribution of the electric field at various wavelengths on the plasmonic surface of gratings.

Figure(4) Electric field and current density distributions for different wavelength

With the fluctuation in wavelength, it was discovered that there is a change in the optical characteristics values that may be displayed in Figure (5). Table (1) provides the optical properties related to absorption, reflection, and transmittance. The absorbance (A) values in Table 1 decrease with increasing wavelength, reflectivity (R) increases with increasing wavelength, and transmittance (T) values are zero for all wavelengths. This is because the surface has attenuated total internal reflection, and the law states that the sum of these optical properties equals one ($A+R+T=1$).

Table (1) Resulted optical properties for plasmonic surface of MSM-Potodetector.

Wavelength	Absorptance	Reflectance	transmittance
450	0.105709	0.89429	0
550	0.051193	0.948806	0
650	0.03267	0.967323	0
750	0.024714	0.97528	0
850	0.01908	0.98091	0
950	0.01516	0.98483	0
1550	0.0059263	0.99407	0
1650	0.0054234	0.99457	0

Figure (5): Absorption, reflectance, and transmittance with different wavelength value.

In addition, the designed circuit shown in Figure (3) was connected to the proposed design for studying the IV-characteristic of MSM-Photodetector with changing the applied voltage from -5V to 5V at different values of λ . As a result, the behaviors of the IV-characteristic of proposed MSM-Photodetector are shown in Figure (6). Where, the crucial factor impacting the photoresponsive and linear characteristics of photodetectors is the measurement of current-voltage at illumination given in Figure (6), which depicts the curve of the change in illumination current values with the photodetector's reverse bias voltage (MSM-photodetector). An increase in incident light power results in an increase in incident photons, which increases the amount of carriers created by photos within depletion region within the carrier diffusion depth, which depends on the lifetime of the minority carriers on both sides of the depletion region. As a result, it is observed the increase in the photocurrent causes an increasing in the bias voltage because the generation of photocarriers leads usually to increase photons.

By using such results of IV-characteristic, the effective factors of designed MSM-Photodetector were tuning and then determined. Table (2) presents the determined values of considered effective factors that gave best properties of MSM-Photodetector at different suitable wavelength ranges.

450nm

550nm

650nm

750nm

850nm

950nm

1550nm

1650nm

Figure (6): IV-characteristic of MSM-Photodetector.

Table (2) Resulted photodetector parameters with λ variation.

450nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	$\eta\%$
R	3.5	1.769* 10^{-6}	0.7523* 10^{-12}	3.545* 10^{-14}	2.82* 10^{13}	5. 99	58. 46	0.5 84
1	3							
R	7.0							
2	7							
R	14.							
3	15							
R	14.							
4	15							
R	21.							
5	22							
550nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	$\eta\%$
R	13.							
1	27							

R 2	26. 54	6.637* 10 ⁻⁶	1.4573* 10 ⁻¹²	2.058* 10 ⁻¹⁴	4.859* 10 ¹³	5. 33	159. 62	1.5 96
R 3	42. 48							
R 4	53. 1							
R 5	70. 8							
650nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	9.5 2	4.760* 10 ⁻⁶	1.234* 10 ⁻¹²	2.376* 10 ⁻¹⁴	4.208* 10 ¹³	5. 45	99.0 11	0. 99
R 2	19. 04							
R 3	34. 62							
R 4	38. 08							
R 5	51. 92							

750nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	7.27	3.635* 10 ⁻⁶	1.078* 10 ⁻¹²	2.966* 10 ⁻¹⁴	3.371* 10 ¹³	4.9 98	60. 07	0. 6
R 2	14.5 4							
R 3	18.1 76							
R 4	22.9							
R 5	36.3 4							

750nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	7.27	3.635* 10 ⁻⁶	1.078* 10 ⁻¹²	2.966* 10 ⁻¹⁴	3.371* 10 ¹³	4.9 98	60. 07	0. 6
R 2	14.5 4							

R 3	18.1 76							
R 4	22.9							
R 5	36.3 4							
850nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	9.9 9	4.998* 10 ⁻⁶	1.264* 10 ⁻¹²	2.173* 10 ⁻¹⁴	4.601* 10 ¹³	5.8 18	84.7 97	0.8 47
R 2	19. 99							
R 3	29. 08							
R 4	39. 98							
R 5	58. 16							

950nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	18. 17	9.008* 10 ⁻⁶	1.6997* 10 ⁻¹	1.948* 10 ⁻¹⁴	5.133* 10 ¹³	4.8 42	11 3.8	1.1 38
R 2	36. 34							
R 3	50. 88							
R 4	72. 7							
R 5	87. 24							

1550nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	19. 08	9.540* 10 ⁻⁶	1.747* 10 ⁻¹²	1.849* 10 ⁻¹⁴	5.408* 10 ¹³	4.9 51	75.5 36	0.7 55
R 2	38. 16							
R 3	50. 88							
R 4	76. 32							
R 5	94. 48							

1650nm		ID	In	NEP	D	G	η	η %
R 1	9.0 84	4.542* 10 ⁻⁶	1.205* 10 ⁻¹²	3.317* 10 ⁻¹⁴	3.317* 10 ¹³	4.00 04	27. 29	0. 27
R 2	18. 17							
R 3	25. 44							
R 4	36. 34							
R 5	36. 34							

Figure (7) demonstrates the photocurrent's relationship to wavelength of MSM-Photodetector, it can be seen that the value of the resulting light current rises with increasing wavelength until it reaches its maximum value at the wavelength (1550 nm) shown in Table (2). Similarly, from Figure (8), the highest values of the spectral response were also found for the two models in Table (2) at the same wavelength, and this wavelength range is in line with earlier studies [16]. Both Figures (7 and 8) illustrate how the values of light current and spectral response as a function of wavelength are divided into three regions: the first is the region of wavelengths less than (750 nm), where the light current and spectral response increase with the increase in wavelength. This occurs because the absorption of wavelengths in the region near the surface because it has a large absorption coefficient, which means a low absorption depth [17]. Whereas, the second is the range of wavelengths between 850 and 1550 nm, which is the region with the maximum spectral response. This range is chosen because it is thought that light absorption takes place within the depletion zone or on its flanks at a distance equal to the depth of carrier propagation. Compared to the initial area in the recombination process, [18], And in the third region, there is a decrease in the value of the response at the wavelength (1650 nm), which can be attributed to the fact that long wavelengths are absorbed by the material, which causes recombination. As a result, the probability of the carriers in the depletion region is little affected by any decrease in responsiveness [17].

Figure (9) displays the values of quantum efficiency as a function of wavelength; few values of the quantitative efficiency generated for the model were noted since the diffusion of charge carriers within the depletion region and the preexisting interlayer from the contact of the metal with the semiconductor; the value of the highest quantitative efficiency was obtained for the two models as given in Table (2), which represents the number of electron hole pairs produced by the photon incident and is therefore recorded as dependent on the type of incident photon (the power of the light source), the device's ability to absorb light, as well as being recorded as a dependence on the interlayer that also mentioned in [19]. In addition, Figure (10) shows the values of the lowest noise equivalent power recorded for the model at the wavelength (1550nm) where the noise current values were different see Table (2), while Figure (11) shows the highest detection of the MSM-Photodetector at the same wavelength.

These results express a successful photodetector design based on using Graphene as a semiconductor material in which the detection response is operated in a wide range of the spectrum extending from visible to infrared. Such design is very useful in physical and medical applications.

Figure (7): Photocurrent as a function of wavelength of MSM-Photodetector.

Figure (8): Responsivity as a function of wavelength of MSM-Photodetector.

Figure (9): Quantum efficiency as a function of wavelength of MSM-Photodetector.

Figure (10): Noise Equevelent Poweras afunction of wavelength of MSM-Photodetector.

Figure (11): Detectivity as afunction of wavelength of MSM-Photodetector.

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